

Analysis and Risk Control of Primary Care Application Evaluation Results Using the PIECES Framework Approach in Primary Health Facilities Work Areas of the Social Security Organizing Agency (BPJS) Health Depok Branch

Author's Details: Evy Nur Erlangga Santi¹, Setia Wirawan²

^{1, 2}Business Information System, Gunadarma University Depok, West Java, Indonesia

Abstract

The National Health Insurance Program (JKN) is organized by Health BPJS focusing on health by using the Health BPJS to provide optimal health services. Therefore, primary health care services must be maintained in quality. To find out whether information regarding primary health information, namely Primary Care applications located in the Depok BPJS Health work area, will be carried out with the best quality, so the activities of the information system are needed. Evaluation is in the form of activities aimed at realizing what is done by using instruments and results to find conclusions, so that problems can arise. The priority is compilation of conclusions from the lowest predicate. Audit systems produce, can be done with several analysis models. In this study, PIECES Framework analysis will be used model, because it is a tool in analysing computer-based information systems, where various factors can be used to analyse such performance, such as performance, information, economy, control, efficiency, and service are needed. By using PIECES as a system analysis tool, appropriate information systems, diagrams and diagrams can be used easily using diagrams that can be used to develop BPJS Health.

Keywords: BPJS Primary Care Health Applications, PIECES, Fishbone, Pareto, Risk Control

1. INTRODUCTION

The National Health Insurance Program (JKN) organized by BPJS Health focuses on the needs of health services in Primary Health Facilities in collaboration with BPJS Health must provide health services in the form of promotion, preventive, accurate, rehabilitative, midwifery services and medical emergency health services including supporting services which include simple laboratory examinations, drug services and referral. This principle will impose health services will be focused on primary health care services such as health centers, clinics and individual practice doctors who will be the main gate of BPJS Health participants in accessing health services. Therefore the quality of primary health care services must be maintained.

Applications that have been developed need to be evaluated also in order to make continuous improvements. There are several ways to measure an information system application, one of which is the PIECES framework analysis method (Supriyatna & Maria, 2017).

The use of PIECES method in evaluating the Primary Care BPJS Health application is the Fishbone and Pareto diagrams.

The Fishbone and Pareto principles can be used to identify and evaluate various problems and their causes (Joshi & Kadam, 2014). Therefore this study uses PIECES framework and its supporting tools using Fishbone and Pareto diagrams.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Analysis

The method used in this study is to use qualitative methods with inductive data analysis. The reason for using data analysis inductively is because the inductive process can find the plural facts contained in the data, besides inductive analysis can make the relationship between the researcher and the respondent become explicit and recognizable.

2.2. Sample Selection

The method used in this study is to use qualitative methods with inductive data analysis. The reason for using data analysis inductively is because the inductive process can find the plural facts contained in the data, besides inductive analysis can make the relationship between the researcher and the respondent become explicit and recognizable.

a. Population

The population in this study were officers who used a library information system consisting of 10 Health BPJS officers consisting of Primary Health Facilities, Primary Benefit Assurance (PMP) staff and IT Helpdesk staff.

b. Research Respondents

The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, where the samples selected in this study were people who were experts or professionals in the field and worked at the BPJS Health Depok Branch.

2.3. Method of collecting data

a. Primary Data

The primary data used in this study were sourced from Primary Benefit Assurance Officers, Primary Health Care Facility Officers and BPJS Health IT Helpdesk, in the form of an overview of the Primary Care information system by conducting a survey by giving questionnaires to 10 selected respondents.

b. Secondary Data

Secondary data used is obtained through literature or literature studies such as books, journals, proceedings and pages. In addition the author also uses data documentation related to data processing carried out by BPJS Primary Care information system in accordance with the research topic.

2.4. Research Instruments

The instrument used to collect data, and will be used to make measurements with the aim of producing accurate data, that is, with a scale. The scale used in this study is a Likert scale with 4 (four) scales. The use of this Likert scale is adjusted to the data needs to be taken is a definite answer, not an answer that is still in doubt or neutral, because the sample selected in this study is someone who is an expert or professional in the field and works at the BPJS Health Depok Branch and later the results of the analysis are quantitative data which will be described as qualitative data. In addition, validity tests were conducted to obtain validity and reliability testing to obtain consistency from a series of measurements on a questionnaire.

Below is a table of questionnaire scores which is then used as a reference for evaluating respondents' perceptions in the form of conclusions about PIECES (Table 1), as follows:

Table 1. Questionnaire score

No	Answer Options	Abbreviation	Score
1	Strongly Agree	SS	4
2	Agree	S	3
3	Disagree	TS	2
4	Strongly Disagree	STS	1

This is the opposite if the question is negative. Then the amount is calculated by the formula:

$$T \times P_n \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

- T = total number of respondents who choose
- P_n = choice of likert score

To get the results of the interpretation, first must know the highest score (X) and the lowest score (Y), for the assessment items with the following formula:

- Y = highest likert score x number of respondents
- X = the lowest likert score x number of respondents

2.5. Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this study is descriptive qualitative, because it has the aim to provide an overview of the extent to which the BPJS primary care information system can be used and useful for parties who have interests, especially officers in Primary Benefit Guarantee, Primary Health Facility Officers and IT Helpdesk BPJS Health. This analysis is also an analysis that is not stated in quantitative calculations but rather processes and describes problems one by one according to the PIECES approach (Performance, Information, Economy, Control, Efficiency, Service) Framework. With this framework, new things can be produced that can be taken into consideration in the continuous improvement of the system.

2.6. Fishbone and Pareto Analysis

This fishbone analysis aims to find the root of the level of approval based on the PIECES (Performance, Information, Economy, Control, Efficiency and Service) approach.

Pareto diagrams are intended to help focus attention on problem solving efforts, so that priority matters can be identified from the results of the results obtained from PIECES analysis.

2.7. Risk Control Analysis

To reduce the likelihood of loss and reduce the severity if a risk does occur, risk control is the PIECES and Pareto analysis.

Figure 1. Three scale risk map matrix

The use of a three-scale risk map matrix (Figure 1.) Is adjusted to the data needs to be taken, which are limited to frequency rarely, sometimes and often, then limited to having an impact on low, medium and high levels, because the risks analyzed are only limited to qualitative which is used to provide a general description of the level of risk.

3. DISCUSSION

PIECES analysis results using a questionnaire on the Primary Care BPJS Health Depok Branch are as follows:

3.1. Validity Test Results

Validity test is used to find out the validity of questionnaires or questionnaires in collecting data. Validity test is done by using bivariate person correlation formula with SPSS version 23. The questionnaire item is valid if the r_count value > r_tabel is 5% significance value. Instead the item is said to be invalid if the r_count < r_tabel is at the 5% significance value. The summary of the validity test results as the data in the following table:

Table 2. Validity test results of PIECES questionnaire against applications primary care (X1)

Item No.	r_count	r_table 5% (10)	Description
P1	0.926	0.6319	Valid
P2	0.666	0.6319	Valid
P3	0.937	0.6319	Valid
P4	0.657	0.6319	Valid
P5	0.662	0.6319	Valid
P6	0.798	0.6319	Valid
P7	0.766	0.6319	Valid
P8	0.926	0.6319	Valid
P9	0.739	0.6319	Valid

The calculation results of the validity test as Table 1, Show that all r_count values > rtablel at a significance value of 5%. Therefore, it can be concluded that all items or statements in this research questionnaire are valid, so that they can be used as research instruments.

3.2. Reliability Test Results

Reliability testing is done using the alpha formula. Significant test was carried out at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The instrument can be said to be reliable or consistent, if the alpha value > r table (0.6319).

Table 3. PIECES questionnaire reliability test results for primary care applications

Variable	Alpha	r_table 5% (10)	Description
X1	0.782	0.6319	Reliable

Reliability Test Results as Table 2, Obtained the value of the reliability coefficient questionnaire X1 of 0.6319, this indicates that the alpha value > r table. Based on the reliability coefficient value, it can be concluded that all questionnaires or questionnaires in this study are reliable or consistent, so that they can be used as instruments in research.

3.3. Result

Table 4. Final results of questionnaire data processing

Category	Indicator	Statement	Total Score	Index %	Description
Performance	Throughput	P1	33	82.50%	Strongly Agree
	Response Time	P2	27	67.50%	Agree
Information	Accurate	P3	32	80.00%	Strongly Agree
	Relevant	P4	29	72.50%	Agree
Economy	Cost	P5	32	80.00%	Strongly Agree
Control	Authorization of System	P6	31	77.50%	Strongly Agree
Efficiency	Flexibility	P7	28	70.00%	Agree
	Productivity	P8	23	57.50%	Agree
Service	Service	P9	26	65.00%	Agree

In this study to state the comparison of each PIECES indicator to the whole is to use a fishbone diagram oriented to the root problem of the approval predicate index (Figure 2) and pareto oriented to the priority scale so that risk control efforts are carried out (Figure 3.). In addition, Pareto can be used as a tool to show the main problems. In this case the main problem is the condition of the low percentage calculation of the questionnaire.

November 30, 2018

Figure 2. Fishbone PIECES diagram primary care application

The explanation of Figure 2, shows that the overall level of approval is "Agree", but because the index value of the approval agreement is an average of 72.5%, so the below-average value is the root of the problem that needs to be carried out risk control. These values are 67.5% of the Response Time on the Performance category, 57.5% of the Productivity indicator and 70% of the Flexibility indicator on the Efficiency category, 65% of the Service indicator against the Service category.

Figure 3. Pareto PIECES diagram primary care application

Explanation from Figure 3, it is known that the priority scale to be able to control risk is the issue of productivity, service, response time and flexibility. These three problems constitute a unity, so that if one of them experiences a decrease in benefits, it will affect the other as well.

To control priority issues that have the potential to have a negative impact on the survival of a BPJS Primary Care Information system from a survey in this study, the risk control efforts for the evaluation findings are as follows (Table 5 & 6):

Table 5. Risk Management on Indicators of PIECES

November 30, 2018

Evaluation Findings	Possible Risks	Risk Assessment				Risk Control	
		Likelihood	Impact	Risk Level	Status	Now	Future
Low level of perception of productivity.	Affect the low level of services provided by BPJS Health in the context of primary care.	2	3	6	High	Follow up by improving the primary care application so that it suits the needs of BPJS Health's in its efforts to improve the productivity improvement of the performance of primary health facility staff and the primary benefit assurance sector.	Conduct periodic reviews of the primary care application to ensure that in terms of productivity has a positive impact on the efficiency of the performance of BPJS Health officers, so as to provide excellent service.
Low level of perception of service.	Affect the low level of satisfaction to users or customers both internally and externally BPJS Health's.	2	3	6	High	Follow up by improving the primary care application so that it meets the needs of BPJS Health's in its efforts to improve service improvement so that it can lead to customer or customer satisfaction both internal and external Health BPJS.	Conduct periodic reviews of the primary care application to ensure that in terms of service is able to provide excellent service to relevant parts, so as to create harmonious cooperation.
Low level of perception of response time.	Affect negatively on performance, thus impacting on the weak productivity of Primary Care human resources BPJS Health's.	2	3	6	High	Follow up by improving the primary care application to fit the needs of BPJS Health in an effort to improve performance improvements so that the response time is consistent with the user's expectations, the response time in each process change does not exceed 2 seconds.	Conduct periodic reviews of the primary care application to ensure that in the case of response time can produce high productivity of human resources BPJS Health.

Continued Table 5. Risk Management on Indicators of PIECES

Evaluation Findings	Possible Risks	Risk Assessment				Risk Control	
		Likelihood	Impact	Risk Level	Status	Now	Future
Low level of perception of flexibility.	Affect the low level of services provided by BPJS Health in the context of primary care.	2	3	6	High	Follow up by improving the primary care application so that it suits the needs of BPJS Health's in its efforts to improve performance improvements to provide convenience in supporting the work and reduce the level of errors in the primary benefit assurance officers and primary health facilities.	Conduct periodic reviews of the primary care application to ensure that in terms of productivity has a positive impact on the efficiency of the performance of BPJS Health officers, so as to provide excellent service.

Table 6. Risk Management on Categories of PIECES

Evaluation Findings	Possible Risks	Risk Assessment				Risk Control	
		Likelihood	Impact	Risk Level	Status	Now	Future
Low level of perception of efficiency.	Affect the weak level of services provided by BPJS Health in the context of primary care.	2	3	6	High	Follow up by improving the primary care application so that it suits the needs of BPJS Health's in its efforts to improve the efficiency improvement of primary health facility and the primary benefit assurance sector.	Periodic review of the primary care application to ensure that in terms of efficiency it has a positive impact on the services of Health BPJS officers.
Low level of perception of service.	Affect the weak level of satisfaction users or customers both internally and externally Health BPJS.	2	3	6	High	Follow up by improving the primary care application so that it suits the needs of BPJS Health in its efforts to improve service improvement so that it can lead to the satisfaction of users or customers both internal and external BPJS Health.	Periodic review of the primary care application to ensure that in terms of service is able to provide excellent service to the relevant parts, so as to create harmonious cooperation.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study regarding analysis related to Performance, Information, Economy, Control, Efficiency and Service (PIECES) then supported by fishbone and pareto analysis and risk control in BPJS Primary Care applications can be concluded that:

- a. Based on the results of fishbone identification, the overall approval level is "Agree" or the index value of the approval predicate is an average of 72.92% with details of 75% of the Performance category with the analysis indicators namely

throughput and response time, 76.25% of the Information category with analysis indicators that is accurate and relevant, 80% of the Economy category with an analysis indicator that is cost, 77.5% of the Control category with an analysis indicator namely system authorization, 63.75% of the Efficiency category with analysis indicators namely flexibility and productivity and then 65% of the Service category with analysis indicators namely service. Below-average values are the root of the problem so risk control is needed. These values are 63.75% of the Efficiency category with indicators of analysis namely flexibility and productivity and also 65% of the Service category with an analysis indicator that is service. Then from the results of the pareto analysis, the priority scale on the PIECES indicator can be attempted to control risk, namely productivity issues, service, response time and flexibility. While the priority scale in the PIECES category can be attempted to control risk, namely Efficiency and Service issues. All of these problems are unity, so if one of them experiences a decrease in benefits, it will affect the other problem as well.

- b. Based on the risk assessment with likelihood level is sometimes and the level of impact is high, it is included in the high probability predicate. The assessment is for indicators of productivity and flexibility in aspects of efficiency, service in service aspects, and response time on aspects of performance. The set of analysis indicators in the system are interconnected with each other and lead to how to give satisfaction to the user or his customers. The order is if the level of risk is a high performance aspect, it will also affect the efficiency aspect, if the level of risk in the aspect of efficiency is high, it will also affect the service aspect, if the risk level of service aspects is high, it will affect the essence of BPJS Primary Care information system This health, namely satisfaction to users or customers.
- c. Based on the results of the risk control carried out as a corrective action that is following up by improving the primary care application so that it fits the needs of BPJS Health in its efforts to improve improvements in aspects of performance, efficiency and service. Then as a continuous improvement measure that is by periodic review of the primary care application to ensure that in terms of response time, productivity, efficiency and service have a positive or capable impact on achieving user or customer satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- i. Bose, T. K. (2012). *Application of Fishbone Analysis for Evaluating Supply Chain and Business Process-A Case Study on the ST James Hospital. International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC), Vol. 3, No. 2.*
- ii. Darnis, F. & Antoni, D. (2016). *Evaluasi Sistem Informasi Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial Kesehatan di Kota Palembang. SEMNASTIKOM.*
- iii. Heizer dan Render. (2014). *Manajemen Operasi. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.*
- iv. IBI (Ikatan Bankir Indonesia). 2012. *Manajemen Resiko 1: Mengidentifikasi Risiko Pasar, Operasional dan Kredit Bank. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.*
- v. Islam, M., Naisra, S., Pritom, S., K., Rahman, M., A. (2016). *Application of Fishbone Analysis for Evaluating Supply Chain and Business Process- A Case Study on KMART. Industrial Engineering Letters. ISSN 2224-6096 (Paper) ISSN 2225-0581 (online) Vol.6, No.7.*
- vi. ISO 31000:2011. (2011). *Standar Manajemen Risiko - Prinsip dan pedoman (ISO 31000:2009, IDT). SNI ISO 31000:2009, BSN, Jakarta.*
- vii. Joshi A. & Kadam P. (2014). *An Application of Pareto Analysis and Cause Effect Diagram for Minimization of Defects in Manual Casting Process. International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering, ISSN: 2320-2092, Vol. 2, Issue-2.*
- viii. Kadir, A. (2014). *Pengenalan Sistem Informasi Edisi Revisi. Yogyakarta: CV. ANDI OFFSET.*
- ix. Kristanto, A. (2003). *Perancangan Sistem Informasi dan Aplikasinya. Jakarta: Gava Media.*
- x. Meilan, T. M., Raharja, S., & Syamsun, M. (2018). *Analisis Manajemen Risiko Lingkungan, Sosial dan Tata Kelola pada Usaha Budidaya dan Pengolahan Kelapa Sawit (Studi Kasus: PT PP London Sumatra Tbk). Manajemen IKM. ISSN 2085-8418, Vol. 13 No. 1.*
- xi. Prasetyowati, A. & Rahadiyanto, C. (2017). *Rancangan Bridging Sistem Informasi Primary Care (P-Care) pada Dokter Praktek Kota Semarang. Jurnal Manajemen Informasi Kesehatan Indonesia. ISSN: 2337-6007, Vol. 5 No.2.*
- xii. Purba, H. & Siregar, K., N. (2014). *Perancangan Integrasi Primary Care BPJS Kesehatan dan Simpus di Puskesmas Bogor Timur, Kota Bogor Tahun 2014. FKM UI.*
- xiii. Putra, Z. F. S., Sholeh M. & Widyastuti N. (2014). *Analisis Kualitas Layanan Website BTKP-DIY Menggunakan Metode Webquel 4.0. Jurnal JARKOM. ISSN:2338-6312, Vol. 1 No. 2.*
- xiv. Rainer Jr., R. Kelly & Casey G. Cegielski. (2013). *Introduction to Information Systems-fourth edition. Singapore: John Wiley and Sons Singapore pte.ltd.*
- xv. Ramli, Soehatman. (2010). *Pedoman Manajemen Risiko dalam Perspektif K3. Jakarta: Dian Rakyat.*
- xvi. Resnita. (2012). *Pengembangan Skala Model Likert. Edu-Bio, Vol.3, 2012.*
- xvii. Rismawati. (2015). *Pelayanan BPJS Kesehatan Masyarakat di Puskesmas Karang Asem Kecamatan Sungai Kunjang Kota Samarinda. eJournal Administrasi Negara. 1668-1682. Vol. 3, No. 5.*
- xviii. Romney, Marshall B., & Steinbart, Paul J. (2012). *Accounting Information Systems. Global Edition. Twelfth Edition. England: Pearson Education Limited.*
- xix. Sarosa, S. (2012). *Metodologi Pengembangan Sistem Informasi. Jakarta: Indeks.*
- xx. Sugiyono. (2012). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R & D. Bandung: CV. ALFABETA.*
- xxi. Supriyatna, A. (2015). *Analisis dan Evaluasi Kepuasan Pengguna Sistem Informasi Perpustakaan dengan Menggunakan PIECES Framework. Jurnal Pilar Nusa Mandiri, ISSN 1978-1946, Vol. IX No. 1.*

November 30, 2018

- xxii. *Supriyatna, A. & Maria, V. (2017). Analisis Tingkat Kepuasan Pengguna dan Tingkat Kepentingan Penerapan Sistem Informasi DJP Online dengan Kerangka PIECES. Jurnal Ilmu Komputer dan Informatika, ISSN 2477-698X, Vol.3 No. 2.*
- xxiii. *Sutabri, T. (2012). Analisis Sistem Informasi. Yogyakarta: CV. ANDI OFFSET.*
- xxiv. *Yakub. (2012). Pengantar Sistem Informasi. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.*
- xxv. *Whitten, J. L. & Bentley, L. D. (2007). Systems Analysis and Design Methods, New York: McGraw-Hill.*